

ESTIMATION OF BISMUTH. PART IV. COLORIMETRIC ANALYSIS WITH DIMERCAPTOTHIOBIAZOLE

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Estimation and separation of bismuth (to the extent of 3γ in 20 c.c.) from other elements have been investigated by following a colorimetric method using dimercaptiothiothiazole in presence of protective colloid (gum acacia) and nitric acid. Effect of diverse ions on the colour has also been examined. The peak of the absorption band of the colour system with spectrophotometer has been found to be at 470 mμ and the variation of the intensity of colour has been found to obey Beer's law at all concentrations of Bi.

During his investigations on the colorimetric estimation of bismuth by thiocyanate, Mahr (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1933, **94**, 261; 1934, **97**, 96) observed that the absorption curves of the coloured complexes of bismuth with thiourea and that with thiocyanate were practically identical. He therefore suggested a co-ordinate bond between the bismuth and the sulphur atom (*cf.* Dubsy, Okac and Okac, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1934, **216**, 386).

The reagent dimercaptiothiothiazole (Lesanitsch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 2544) having the reacting group $N=(HS)C-S-C(SH)=N$, forms with bismuth a coloured complex which, it has been shown here, can be utilised for the colorimetric estimation of the element.

Dubsy and Okac (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1934, **96**, 267) used this reagent for the detection of small quantities of bismuth, and found the identification limit to be 1·2 μg. and sensitivity, 1 part in 28,000 parts. Ray and Gupta (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 308), on the other hand, using a nitric acid solution of bismuth, and not hydrochloric acid solution, as used by Dubsy and his co-workers (*loc. cit.*), found that the identification limit could be extended to 0·1 μg. and sensitivity, to one part in 1,600,000 parts. The author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **19**, 396) however, using the reagent, has observed that if the red precipitate obtained by the reagent with the bismuth nitrate solution is peptised by a protective colloid as gum acacia, the coloration limit extends further to 1 part in 6,000,000 parts and that the colour, developed, ranging from red to yellow, depending upon the concentration of bismuth, may be used for the estimation of bismuth, even up to the extent of 3γ in 20 c.c. solution as the intensity of colour varies regularly according to Beer's law in all concentrations studied, with the help of a variable depth type colour comparator (Dubosq type). Effects of diverse ions on the colour system has also been examined.

With spectrophotometer of Schmidt and Haensch, the peak of the absorption band of the colour system has been found to be at 470 mμ and that the Beer's law is followed by the colour system has further been verified by the fact that a straight line resulted by plotting the logarithms of the observed transmittances at 470 mμ against the respective bismuth concentrations.

It is known that like hydrogen sulphide, the reagent dimercaptiothiothiazole behaves as a weak acid and forms characteristic coloured precipitates with most of the metals of the H₂S group of the analytical table. With the idea of separating bismuth from these elements, the effect of organic solvents on the compounds of metals with the reagent has been examined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents.—All reagents used were of 'pro analyse' variety of Schering and Kahlbaum, except the gum acacia which is of Evans Sons Lescher and Webb Ltd. (London).

Dimercaptiothiothiazole (C₂N₂S₂H₂), m.p. 168-69°, was prepared and recrystallised by the method of Losanitsch (*loc. cit.*) and kept in an orange coloured desiccator. A solution containing 0·5% of the reagent in water was used. The solution was colourless when first prepared but slowly, on keeping over night, some yellow precipitate separated, due probably to the formation of insoluble disulphide. Solution from freshly prepared reagent was more sensitive

than the solution from the reagent prepared a few months back. This latter solution was again more sensitive than the solution kept for a week.

Bismuth.—Solutions of bismuth nitrate were prepared from sub-nitrates with water and a few c.c. of concentrated nitric acid to keep the bismuth in solution, and the bismuth contents per c.c. were determined by the oxide method (Miller and Van Dyke Cruser, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 27, 116). From these standard solutions, solutions containing different amounts of bismuth per c.c., were prepared by dilution.

Gum acacia.—A 0.5% aqueous solution.

Nitric acid.—A normal solution of nitric acid in water.

General Procedure.—A few c.c. of the prepared bismuth solution, faintly acidic with dilute nitric acid, is taken in a tube of the Dubosq colorimeter and to that is added about 5 c.c. of $N\text{-HNO}_3$, a few c.c. of gum acacia solution (5 c.c.), a few c.c. water and a few drops of the reagent solution till the maximum colour is developed. The total volume of the solution is maintained at 20 c.c. During the addition of the reagent the solution is gently swirled to facilitate thorough mixing. The solution is then allowed to stand for five minutes and the colour compared. An excess of the reagent solution or the solution of gum acacia, has no influence on the colour system. If the solution contains large amounts of electrolytes, excess of gum acacia solution should be added to stabilise the colloidal suspension of the bismuth compound.

The intensity of colour has been found to increase with the increase of concentration of nitric acid. A limit of increasing intensity with the concentration of nitric acid has been observed. Intensity increased up to the conc. of 5 c.c. $N\text{-HNO}_3$ in a 20 c.c. soln., thereafter no further increase was observed even when the concentration of acid was extended to 10 c.c. As nitric acid has an influence on the colour system, it is always advisable to use the same quantity of nitric acid both for the unknown and for the standard. Even though the reagent or the gum acacia has been found to have no influence on the colour system, the same amount of them was used for the unknown and the standard as well. Results are given below :

Bi taken.	Bi found.	Error.	Bi taken.	Bi found.	Error.
1.49 mg.	1.48 mg.	-0.01 mg.	0.068	0.069	+0.001
2.90	2.87	-0.03	0.01	0.01	nil
0.48	0.49	+0.01	0.003	0.003	nil
1.02	1.03	+0.01	6.48	6.43	-0.05
0.68	0.68	nil	3.888	3.90	+0.012

For the estimation of bismuth of the order of a milligram or higher, one should take the bismuth nitrate solution (containing some free nitric acid to keep the bismuth in solution) in a 100 c.c. volumetric flask, add 5-10 c.c. of normal nitric acid, a few c.c. gum sufficient to peptise the bismuth compound, dilute almost to the mark with water, add a few c.c. of the reagent solution till there is no further increase in colour, then make up to the mark with water and mix thoroughly. Colour comparison should be made, about five minutes, after the addition of the reagent, in the tubes of the comparator as usual.

Conformity to Beer's Law.—That Beer's law is followed by the colour system, through a long range of concentration of bismuth studied, is evident from the graphs given (Figs. 1-4) by plotting the reciprocal colorimetric readings on the abscissa and the concentrations on the ordinates.

Stability of the Colour.—In addition to gum acacia, other substances as glycerine, agar-agar, etc. stabilise the colloidal suspension as well. A cream coloured precipitate is obtained when the reagent solution is added to the bismuth solution containing gelatine.

When the bismuth solution contains just sufficient nitric acid to prevent hydrolysis, gum acacia required to stabilise is very small in quantity, even 0.5 c.c. is found to be more than sufficient. For the same amount of nitric acid, the amount of gum acacia should be increased if the amount of bismuth is increased, and for the same amount of bismuth the amount of gum acacia should be increased, if the amount of nitric acid is increased.

The colour system keeps well without coagulation for about twelve hours when the bismuth concentration is about 10^{-4} g. or less, but with bismuth of higher concentration it keeps well for about an hour.

Interference.—To study the effects of diverse ions on the colour system, standard solutions of them were prepared from the chloride, nitrate or sulphate salts of the cations from the sodium or potassium salts of the anions. As stated earlier, a number of ions gave reactions with the reagent in neutral or acid solutions. The possible interference of a number of ions was determined under the conditions recommended in the general procedure, using bismuth concentration of 0.26 mg.

The following coloured ions interfere only if present at concentrations exceeding that required to produce the colour due to the ion itself. The limiting concentrations are: Cu^{++} , 0.07 mg.; Co^{++} , 2.5 mg.; Ni^{++} , 9 mg.

The following ions are without effect even at a concentration of: Zn^{++} , 100 mg.; Mn^{++} , 100 mg.; Fe^{++} , 100 mg.; $\text{SO}_4^{//}$, 100 mg.; $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{O}_6^{//}$, 100 mg.; 10 c.c. H_2SO_3 (saturated solution); 1 c.c. H_3PO_2 (*d.*, 1.274).

The limiting concentrations, for the interfering ions due to precipitations, are Cd^{++} , 3 mg.; Pb^{++} , 5 mg.; Hg^{++} , 1 mg.; Ag^+ , 0.5 mg.; $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{//}$, 50 mg.; Cl^+ , 50 mg.; As^{+++} , 5 mg.; Sb^{+++} , 0.2 mg.; Sn^{++} , 1 mg. Concentration of the interfering ions can be increased if the concentration of nitric acid is increased.

In presence of phosphate ions, bismuth can be estimated by adding sufficient nitric acid to dissolve the precipitate due to phosphate. Thus by adding one c.c. excess, to that required to dissolve the precipitate, of concentrated HNO_3 , bismuth is estimated in presence of 100 mg. of phosphate ions. Similarly by adding 5 c.c. of twice normal nitric acid, bismuth is determined in presence of 100 mg. of chloride or oxalate ions.

Estimation of Bismuth in presence of other Ions.—Bismuth was precipitated as phenylarsonate (Part IV of this series). Thus separated, from a number of interfering ions, the precipitate was well washed with hot water, dissolved by heating with 1 c.c. concentrated nitric acid and made up to the mark with water in a 100 c.c. volumetric flask. An aliquot part of this solution, was taken in the colorimeter tube and to that were added 5 c.c. of normal nitric acid, 5 c.c. gum, diluted with water and a few drops of the reagent solution till there was no further increase in colour. Total volume of the solution was maintained at 20 c.c. The solution was thoroughly mixed and the colour compared, after standing for 5 minutes, against a standard prepared in the same way.

Results are given below.

Bi taken.	Bi found.	Bi taken.	Bi found.
0.20 mg.	0.195 mg.	0.025 mg.	0.0252 mg.
0.02	0.0196	0.0389	0.0383

Spectrophotometric study.—For the spectrophotometric studies, Schmidt and Haensch spectrophotometer was used with a cell of thickness 7.5 mm. and a spectral band width of 10 μ . To study the wave-length of maximum absorption, 5 c.c. of the bismuth nitrate solution (0.6 mg. Bi), acidified with dilute nitric acid to keep bismuth in solution, were taken in a bottle. To this was added 11 c.c. of water, 2 c.c. gum acacia, 2 c.c. reagent and mixed thoroughly. A part of this solution was then taken in the cell and by varying the wave-length of light, the absorptions in different regions were measured. By plotting the logarithms of

the observed transmittances against wave-lengths, region of maximum absorption was found to be at 470 μ . (Fig. 5)

Bear's Law.—That Beer's law is obeyed by this colour system, is shown by the fact that a straight line resulted when the logarithm of the observed transmittances at 470 μ , for a number of solutions, containing from 65 p. p.m. to 650 p. p.m. of bismuth, were plotted against the respective concentrations (Fig. 6).

During the spectrophotometric studies, the reagent solution or the solution of gum acacia has been found to have no absorption in the visible region.

Solubility of the Salts formed by the Metals with the Reagent in Organic Solvents.—The bismuth compound of the reagent has been found to be soluble in alcohols, such as methyl, ethyl, propyl (normal and *iso*), *iso*amyl, and also in acetone, ethyl acetate, pyridine and ether; sparingly soluble in carbon disulphide, and insoluble in chloroform, benzene and carbon tetrachloride.

The compounds formed by lead, manganese, copper, cadmium, mercury (*ic*), cobalt and silver are insoluble in chloroform, *iso*amyl alcohol, ether and in acetone; that of nickel and zinc are soluble in acetone but insoluble in chloroform, *iso*amylalcohol and in ether; compound with tin (*ous*) is soluble in *iso*amyl alcohol, ether and in acetone but insoluble in chloroform and that of antimony is soluble in *iso*amyl alcohol and in acetone but insoluble in chloroform and in ether.

Further work on the estimation and separation of bismuth from other elements by extracting with organic solvents is in progress.

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